

Choosing the Best Investment according to the Financial Factors in the Neutrosophic Binary Environment

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Abstract. Investment analysis is a process of choosing the best investment sector that helps the employee to invest in a good manner. The process is done using the neutrosophic binary sets which contains the contains truth value, indeterminacy and falsehood value. This evaluating process needs experts knowledge and judgments. Neutrosophic binary set theory is a useful technique to capture experts evaluations. This paper proposes the new present worth and future worth analysis techniques with neutrosophic binary sets. An illustrative example shows the applicability of the techniques. Comparison analyses are realized with classical and simplified neutrosophic binary present and future worth techniques. The comparison results show that the proposed techniques helps the employee to choose the best investing sector.

Keywords:Neutrosophic Binary Sets, Neutrosophic Binary Similarity measure, Decision making problems, Investment Sectors.

1. Introduction

The higher returns of the stock market in the past long periods compared to other markets have made this market one of the suitable investment options [25]. Analysis of financial statements can be used to evaluate the performance and predict the future of companies [11]. There are different approaches to achieving this goal [16, 36]. Some believe that horizontal and vertical analyzes of financial statements depict a definite trend in a company's financial situation and provide appropriate information about the activities of the company in question [13]. Another approach is to use financial statements for short-term and long-term evaluations of a company's situation, which is critical to focus on parts of the financial statements according to each type of evaluation [18, 38].

For this reason, a different category can be assigned to the analysis of financial statements [20, 28]. Using financial ratio analysis techniques, a better understanding of the financial situation of companies can be obtained. Usually, the calculation of financial ratios is straightforward, but the analysis of these ratios is essential [8, 22]. Analyzing financial statements using some ratios is actually an effort to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of a company by examining the figures stated in the reports. In addition, it was compared to the same ratio last year and with similar ratios in competing companies [29]. These comparisons show the trend of the company's situation during different periods as well as the strength of the company's competition with other companies in its industry. Therefore, investors need to choose the right investment sector, and financial ratios can help investors in this matter [10]. In the MCDM context, the ratings of the options provided by decision-makers can be expressed with the Neutrosophic binary Set Theory.

Fuzzy sets theory has been widely and successfully applied in many different areas to handle such uncertainty [35]. Nevertheless, it presents limitations to dealing with imprecise and vague information when various sources of vagueness appear simultaneously [23]. Between 2019-2024 Smarandache[32] introduced sixteen new types of topologies: Non Standard Topology, Largest Extended Non Standard Real Topology, Neutrosophic Triplet Weak/Strong Topologies, Neutrosophic Extended Triplet Weak/Strong Topologies, Neutrosophic Duplet Topology, Neutrosophic Extended Duplet Topology, Neutrosophic MultiSet Topology, NonStandard Neutrosophic Topology, NeutroTopology, AntiTopology, Refined Neutrosophic Topology, Refined Neutrosophic Crisp Topology, SuperHyperTopology, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperTopology. Smarandache [31, 41] germinated the notion of having a neutrosophic set (NS) holding three different fundamental elements (i) truth, (ii) indeterminate, and (iii) falsity. Each attribute of the neutrosophic sets is relevant to our real-life models [6]. The most exciting point is that all these three functions are entirely independent, and one function is not affected by another [30]. These NSs can handle indeterminate and inconsistent information quite well. Since NSs are difficult to apply in real engineering problems and scientific applications, a subclass of NS has been proposed by Wang et al. [37]. These sets are called single-valued neutrosophic sets. SVNSs are well suited for handling ambiguous, incomplete, imprecise information [21]. Since its appearance and the ability to tackle the indeterminacy at the initial stage of data, SVNS is one of the hot topics to tackle the DMPs [12]. SVNS is one of the most favorable environments to access the alternatives [7]. Ratings of criteria of decision problems can be expressed using linguistic variables that can be transformed into SVNNs [1]. Moreover, many information measures for the SVNS model have been proposed over the years, such as similarity, distance, entropy, inclusion, and correlation coefficients [5]. Many scholars and researchers have continuously proposed new similarity measures for fuzzy-based models, including the SVNS model,

and applied these measures to solve various practical problems related to MCDM [24]. In some real applications and related fields, the researcher uses similarity measure, an important mathematical tool [7].

In today's world, it is hard to tackle with a single universal set. For this purpose, two universal sets that is neutrosophic binary sets which was proposed by Surekha, Elekiah and Sindhu in 2022 [38] was used to solve the decision making problems. Neutrosophic binary sets helps the employees understand the investment analysis in a good manner. As choosing the suitable sector for investment is an MCDM one, including various factors and uncertainty, this article has addressed the idea of choosing that by considering the practical factors as the problem criteria in a neutrosophic binary environment.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [38] A Neutrosophic binary topology from X to Y is a binary structure $M_{\mathcal{N}} \subseteq P(X) \times P(Y)$ that satisfies the following conditions:

- (1) $(0_X, 0_Y) \in M_{\mathcal{N}}$ and $1_X, 1_Y \in M_{\mathcal{N}}$.
- (2) $(A_1 \cap A_2, B_1 \cap B_2) \in M_{\mathcal{N}}$ whenever $(A_1, B_1) \in M_{\mathcal{N}}$ and $(A_2, B_2) \in M_{\mathcal{N}}$.
- (3) If $(A_\alpha, B_\alpha)_{\alpha \in A}$ is a family of members of $M_{\mathcal{N}}$, then $(\cup_{\alpha \in A} A_\alpha, \cup_{\alpha \in A} B_\alpha) \in M_{\mathcal{N}}$.

The triplet $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}, M_{\mathcal{N}})$ is called Neutrosophic Binary Topological space. The members of $M_{\mathcal{N}}$ are called the neutrosophic binary open sets and the complement of neutrosophic binary open sets are called the neutrosophic binary closed sets in the binary topological space $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}, M_{\mathcal{N}})$.

Definition 2.2. [38] $(0_X, 0_Y)$ can be defined as

- (0₁) $0_X = \{ \langle x, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$, $0_Y = \{ \langle y, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : y \in Y \}$
- (0₂) $0_X = \{ \langle x, 0, 1, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$, $0_Y = \{ \langle y, 0, 1, 1 \rangle : y \in Y \}$
- (0₃) $0_X = \{ \langle x, 0, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$, $0_Y = \{ \langle y, 0, 1, 0 \rangle : y \in Y \}$
- (0₄) $0_X = \{ \langle x, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$, $0_Y = \{ \langle y, 0, 0, 0 \rangle : y \in Y \}$

$(1_X, 1_Y)$ can be defined as

- (1₁) $1_X = \{ \langle x, 1, 0, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$, $1_Y = \{ \langle y, 1, 0, 0 \rangle : y \in Y \}$
- (1₂) $1_X = \{ \langle x, 1, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$, $1_Y = \{ \langle y, 1, 0, 1 \rangle : y \in Y \}$
- (1₃) $1_X = \{ \langle x, 1, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$, $1_Y = \{ \langle y, 1, 1, 0 \rangle : y \in Y \}$
- (1₄) $1_X = \{ \langle x, 1, 1, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$, $1_Y = \{ \langle y, 1, 1, 1 \rangle : y \in Y \}$

Definition 2.3. [38] Let $(A, B) = \{ \langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \gamma_A \rangle, \langle \mu_B, \sigma_B, \gamma_B \rangle \}$ be a neutrosophic binary set on $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}, M_N)$, then the complement of the set $C(A, B)$ may be defined as

$$(C_1) \quad C(A, B) = \{ x, \langle 1 - \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), 1 - \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X, \\ \langle y, 1 - \mu_B(y), \sigma_B(y), 1 - \gamma_B(y) \rangle : y \in Y \}$$

$$(C_2) \quad C(A, B) = \{ x, \langle \gamma_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X, \\ \langle y, \gamma_B(y), \sigma_B(y), \mu_B(y) \rangle : y \in Y \}$$

$$(C_3) \quad C(A, B) = \{ x, \langle \gamma_A(x), 1 - \sigma_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X, \\ \langle y, \gamma_B(y), 1 - \sigma_B(y), \mu_B(y) \rangle : y \in Y \}$$

Definition 2.4. [38] Let (A, B) and (C, D) be two neutrosophic binary sets which is in the form

$$(A, B) = \{ \langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \gamma_A \rangle, \langle \mu_B, \sigma_B, \gamma_B \rangle \} \text{ and}$$

$$(C, D) = \{ \langle \mu_C, \sigma_C, \gamma_C \rangle, \langle \mu_D, \sigma_D, \gamma_D \rangle \}.$$

Then $(A, B) \subseteq (C, D)$ can be defined as

$$(1) \quad (A, B) \subseteq (C, D) \iff \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_C(x), \sigma_A(x) \leq \sigma_C(x), \gamma_A(x) \geq \gamma_C(x) \forall x \in X \\ \mu_B(x) \leq \mu_D(x), \sigma_B(x) \leq \sigma_D(x), \gamma_B(x) \geq \gamma_D(x) \forall y \in Y$$

$$(2) \quad (A, B) \subseteq (C, D) \iff \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_C(x), \sigma_A(x) \geq \sigma_C(x), \gamma_A(x) \geq \gamma_C(x) \forall x \in X \\ \mu_B(x) \leq \mu_D(x), \sigma_B(x) \geq \sigma_D(x), \gamma_B(x) \geq \gamma_D(x) \forall y \in Y$$

Definition 2.5. [38] Let (A, B) and (C, D) be two neutrosophic binary sets which is in the form

$$(A, B) = \{ \langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \gamma_A \rangle, \langle \mu_B, \sigma_B, \gamma_B \rangle \} \text{ and}$$

$$(C, D) = \{ \langle \mu_C, \sigma_C, \gamma_C \rangle, \langle \mu_D, \sigma_D, \gamma_D \rangle \}.$$

(1) $(A, B) \cap (C, D)$ can be defined as

$$(A, B) \cap (C, D) = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_C(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_C(x), \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_C(x) \rangle \\ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_C(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_C(x), \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_C(x) \rangle \}$$

$$(A, B) \cap (C, D) = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_C(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_C(x), \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_C(x) \rangle \\ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_C(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_C(x), \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_C(x) \rangle \}$$

(2) $(A, B) \cup (C, D)$ can be defined as

$$(A, B) \cup (C, D) = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_C(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_C(x), \gamma_A(x) \wedge \gamma_C(x) \rangle \\ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_C(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_C(x), \gamma_A(x) \wedge \gamma_C(x) \rangle \}$$

$$(A, B) \cup (C, D) = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_C(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_C(x), \gamma_A(x) \wedge \gamma_C(x) \rangle \\ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_C(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_C(x), \gamma_A(x) \wedge \gamma_C(x) \rangle \}$$

Definition 2.6 (5). Let A and B be the two neutrosophic sets over the universe X . The neutrosophic similarity measure based on set theoretic approach is defined by

$S(A, B) = S_T(A, B), S_I(A, B), S_F(A, B)$, where

$$S_T(A, B) = \frac{1}{n} \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n [(T_A(x_i) \wedge T_B(x_i))]}{\sum_{i=1}^n [T_A(x_i) \vee T_B(x_i)]} \right] \implies \text{Degree of similarity}$$

$$S_I(A, B) = 1 - \frac{1}{n} \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n [(I_A(x_i) \wedge I_B(x_i))]}{\sum_{i=1}^n [I_A(x_i) \vee I_B(x_i)]} \right] \implies \text{Degree of Indeterminancy}$$

$$S_F(A, B) = 1 - \frac{1}{n} \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n [(F_A(x_i) \wedge F_B(x_i))]}{\sum_{i=1}^n [F_A(x_i) \vee F_B(x_i)]} \right] \implies \text{Degree of non-similarity}$$

3. Similarity measure based on set theoretic approach

Definition 3.1. Let $\mathcal{S}_U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ and $\mathcal{S}_V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ be the two universal sets. Let (I_1, I_2) and (J_1, J_2) be the two neutrosophic binary sets over the universe $\mathcal{S}_U \times \mathcal{S}_V$.

The neutrosophic binary similarity measure based on set theoretic approach is denoted by $S^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)]$ and is defined by

$S^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] = S_\mu^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)], S_\sigma^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)], S_\gamma^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)]$, For all $u_i \in \mathcal{S}_U$ and $v_j \in \mathcal{S}_V$

$$S_\mu^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] = \frac{1}{n} \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n [(\mu_{I_1}(u_i) \wedge \mu_{J_1}(u_i))]}{\sum_{i=1}^n [(\mu_{I_1}(u_i) \vee \mu_{J_1}(u_i))]} + \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n [(\mu_{I_2}(v_j) \wedge \mu_{J_2}(v_j))]}{\sum_{j=1}^n [(\mu_{I_2}(v_j) \vee \mu_{J_2}(v_j))]} \right]$$

$$S_\sigma^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] = 1 - \frac{1}{n} \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n [(\sigma_{I_1}(u_i) \wedge \sigma_{J_1}(u_i))]}{\sum_{i=1}^n [(\sigma_{I_1}(u_i) \vee \sigma_{J_1}(u_i))]} + \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n [(\sigma_{I_2}(v_j) \wedge \sigma_{J_2}(v_j))]}{\sum_{j=1}^n [(\sigma_{I_2}(v_j) \vee \sigma_{J_2}(v_j))]} \right]$$

$$S_\gamma^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] = 1 - \frac{1}{n} \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n [(\gamma_{I_1}(u_i) \wedge \gamma_{J_1}(u_i))]}{\sum_{i=1}^n [(\gamma_{I_1}(u_i) \vee \gamma_{J_1}(u_i))]} + \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n [(\gamma_{I_2}(v_j) \wedge \gamma_{J_2}(v_j))]}{\sum_{j=1}^n [(\gamma_{I_2}(v_j) \vee \gamma_{J_2}(v_j))]} \right]$$

Here, $S_\mu^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)]$ denotes the degree of similarity where the truth membership values are considered, $S_\sigma^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)]$ denotes the degree of indeterminacy where the indeterminate values are considered and $S_\gamma^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)]$ denotes the degree of non-similarity where the false membership values are considered.

Theorem 3.2 (Axioms of Similarity). *For the neutrosophic binary sets (I_1, I_2) , (J_1, J_2) and (K_1, K_2) over the universe $\mathcal{S}_U \times \mathcal{S}_V$, the following are true:*

$$\begin{aligned}
 & S^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] = S^M[(J_1, J_2), (I_1, I_2)]. \quad 0 \leq S^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] \leq 1. \\
 & S^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] = 1 \text{ if and only if } (I_1, I_2) = (J_1, J_2). \quad \text{Let} \\
 & (I_1, I_2) \subseteq (J_1, J_2) \subseteq (K_1, K_2), \text{ then } S^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] \geq S^M[(I_1, I_2), (K_1, K_2)] \text{ and} \\
 & S^M[(J_1, J_2), (K_1, K_2)] \geq S^M[(I_1, I_2), (K_1, K_2)].
 \end{aligned}$$

(1) Proof. The proof for (i), (ii) and (iii) are obvious from the definition 3.1.

Let $(I_1, I_2) \subseteq (J_1, J_2) \subseteq (K_1, K_2)$.

For all $u_i \in \mathcal{S}_U$ and $v_j \in \mathcal{S}_V$

$$\mu_{I_1}(u_i) \leq \mu_{J_1}(u_i) \leq \mu_{K_1}(u_i) ; \mu_{I_2}(v_j) \leq \mu_{J_2}(v_j) \leq \mu_{K_2}(v_j).$$

$$\sigma_{I_1}(u_i) \geq \sigma_{J_1}(u_i) \geq \sigma_{K_1}(u_i) ; \sigma_{I_2}(v_j) \geq \sigma_{J_2}(v_j) \geq \sigma_{K_2}(v_j).$$

$$\gamma_{I_1}(u_i) \geq \gamma_{J_1}(u_i) \geq \gamma_{K_1}(u_i) ; \gamma_{I_2}(v_j) \geq \gamma_{J_2}(v_j) \geq \gamma_{K_2}(v_j).$$

Now, for all $u_i \in \mathcal{S}_U$ and $v_j \in \mathcal{S}_V$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\mu_{I_1}(u_i) \wedge \mu_{J_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{I_1}(u_i) \vee \mu_{J_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{I_2}(v_j) \wedge \mu_{J_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{I_2}(v_j) \vee \mu_{J_2}(v_j)} = \frac{\mu_{I_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{J_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{I_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{J_2}(v_j)} \\
 & \frac{\mu_{I_1}(u_i) \wedge \mu_{K_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{I_1}(u_i) \vee \mu_{K_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{I_2}(v_j) \wedge \mu_{K_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{I_2}(v_j) \vee \mu_{K_2}(v_j)} = \frac{\mu_{I_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{K_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{I_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{K_2}(v_j)} \\
 & \frac{\mu_{J_1}(u_i) \wedge \mu_{K_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{J_1}(u_i) \vee \mu_{K_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{J_2}(v_j) \wedge \mu_{K_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{J_2}(v_j) \vee \mu_{K_2}(v_j)} = \frac{\mu_{J_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{K_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{J_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{K_2}(v_j)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left[\frac{\mu_{I_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{K_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{I_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{K_2}(v_j)} \right] &= \left[\frac{\mu_{J_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{K_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{J_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{K_2}(v_j)} \right] + \left[\frac{\mu_{I_1}(u_i) - \mu_{J_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{K_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{I_2}(v_j) - \mu_{J_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{K_2}(v_j)} \right] \\
 &\leq \left[\frac{\mu_{J_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{K_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{J_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{K_2}(v_j)} \right] \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Also, since $\mu_{J_1}(u_i) \leq \mu_{K_1}(u_i)$ and $\mu_{J_2}(v_j) \leq \mu_{K_2}(v_j)$,

$$\frac{\mu_{I_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{K_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{I_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{K_2}(v_j)} \leq \frac{\mu_{I_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{J_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{I_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{J_2}(v_j)} \quad (2)$$

From (1) and (2),

$$\frac{\mu_{I_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{J_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{I_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{J_2}(v_j)} \geq \frac{\mu_{I_1}(u_i)}{\mu_{K_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\mu_{I_2}(v_j)}{\mu_{K_2}(v_j)}$$

Therefore, $S_{\mu}^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] \geq S_{\mu}^M[(I_1, I_2), (K_1, K_2)]$.

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\sigma}^M[(I_1, I_2), (K_1, K_2)] &= 1 - \left[\frac{\sigma_{I_1}(u_i) \wedge \sigma_{K_1}(u_i)}{\sigma_{I_1}(u_i) \vee \sigma_{K_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\sigma_{I_2}(v_j) \wedge \sigma_{K_2}(v_j)}{\sigma_{I_2}(v_j) \vee \sigma_{K_2}(v_j)} \right] \\ &= 1 - \left[\frac{\sigma_{K_1}(u_i)}{\sigma_{I_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\sigma_{K_2}(v_j)}{\sigma_{I_2}(v_j)} \right] \\ &\geq 1 - \left[\frac{\sigma_{J_1}(u_i)}{\sigma_{I_1}(u_i)} + \frac{\sigma_{J_2}(v_j)}{\sigma_{I_2}(v_j)} \right] \\ &\quad [\text{Since, } \sigma_{K_1}(u_i) \leq \sigma_{J_1}(u_i); \sigma_{K_2}(v_j) \leq \sigma_{J_2}(v_j)] \end{aligned}$$

This implies that, $S_{\sigma}^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] \leq S_{\mu}^M[(I_1, I_2), (K_1, K_2)]$.

Similarly, $S_{\gamma}^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] \leq S_{\gamma}^M[(I_1, I_2), (K_1, K_2)]$.

Hence, $S^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] \geq S^M[(I_1, I_2), (K_1, K_2)]$, where

$$\begin{aligned} S^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)] &= (S_{\mu}^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)], S_{\sigma}^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)], \\ &\quad S_{\gamma}^M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)]) \\ S^M[(I_1, I_2), (K_1, K_2)] &= (S_{\mu}^M[(I_1, I_2), (K_1, K_2)], S_{\sigma}^M[(I_1, I_2), (K_1, K_2)], \\ &\quad S_{\gamma}^M[(I_1, I_2), (K_1, K_2)]) \end{aligned}$$

. Similarly, $S_{\gamma}^M[(J_1, J_2), (K_1, K_2)] \geq S_{\gamma}^M[(I_1, I_2), (K_1, K_2)]$. \square

4. Methodology

Let M_1, M_2, \dots, M_n be the set of male employees and F_1, F_2, \dots, F_n be the set of female employees; $I_{M_1}, I_{M_2}, \dots, I_{M_n}$ be the criteria (investment) of male employees and $I_{F_1}, I_{F_2}, \dots, I_{F_n}$ be the criteria (investment) of female employees; $J_{M_1}, J_{M_2}, \dots, J_{M_n}$ be the alternatives of male employees and $J_{F_1}, J_{F_2}, \dots, J_{F_n}$ be the alternatives of female employees. The ranking of the alternatives is based on the ideas of the employees against the investment chosen by them. This ranking method will be performed by the decision makers. For a MADM problem, the values associated with the alternatives of male and female employees can be represented in a decision matrix which is shown in table 1, table 2.

Here ϕ_{ij} and ψ_{ij} represents the neutrosophic binary sets.

The algorithm for this method is demonstrated below:

Step 1: Deliberate the association between the employees and the attributes.

	(J_{M_1}, J_{F_1})	(J_{M_2}, J_{F_2})	(J_{M_n}, J_{F_n})
(M_1, F_1)	ϕ_{11}	ϕ_{12}	ϕ_{1n}
(M_2, F_2)	ϕ_{21}	ϕ_{22}	ϕ_{2n}
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
(M_n, F_n)	ϕ_{n1}	ϕ_{n2}	ϕ_{nn}

TABLE 1. The relation between employees and attributes

	(I_{M_1}, I_{F_1})	(I_{M_2}, I_{F_2})	(I_{M_n}, I_{F_n})
(J_{M_1}, J_{F_1})	ψ_{11}	ψ_{12}	ψ_{1n}
(J_{M_2}, J_{F_2})	ψ_{21}	ψ_{22}	ψ_{2n}
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
(J_{M_n}, J_{F_n})	ψ_{n1}	ψ_{n2}	ψ_{nn}

TABLE 2. The relation between attributes and alternatives

	(J_{M_1}, J_{F_1})	(J_{M_2}, J_{F_2})	(J_{M_n}, J_{F_n})
(M_1, F_1)	$\langle \mu_{11}(x_i^*), \sigma_{11}(x_i^*), \gamma_{11}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{11}(y_i^*), \sigma_{11}(y_i^*), \gamma_{11}(y_i^*) \rangle$	$\langle \mu_{12}(x_i^*), \sigma_{12}(x_i^*), \gamma_{12}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{12}(y_i^*), \sigma_{12}(y_i^*), \gamma_{12}(y_i^*) \rangle$	$\langle \mu_{1n}(x_i^*), \sigma_{1n}(x_i^*), \gamma_{1n}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{1n}(y_i^*), \sigma_{1n}(y_i^*), \gamma_{1n}(y_i^*) \rangle$
(M_2, F_2)	$\langle \mu_{21}(x_i^*), \sigma_{21}(x_i^*), \gamma_{21}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{21}(y_i^*), \sigma_{21}(y_i^*), \gamma_{21}(y_i^*) \rangle$	$\langle \mu_{22}(x_i^*), \sigma_{22}(x_i^*), \gamma_{22}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{22}(y_i^*), \sigma_{22}(y_i^*), \gamma_{22}(y_i^*) \rangle$	$\langle \mu_{2n}(x_i^*), \sigma_{2n}(x_i^*), \gamma_{2n}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{2n}(y_i^*), \sigma_{2n}(y_i^*), \gamma_{2n}(y_i^*) \rangle$
...
(M_n, F_n)	$\langle \mu_{n1}(x_i^*), \sigma_{n1}(x_i^*), \gamma_{n1}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{n1}(y_i^*), \sigma_{n1}(y_i^*), \gamma_{n1}(y_i^*) \rangle$	$\langle \mu_{n2}(x_i^*), \sigma_{n2}(x_i^*), \gamma_{n2}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{n2}(y_i^*), \sigma_{n2}(y_i^*), \gamma_{n2}(y_i^*) \rangle$	$\langle \mu_{nn}(x_i^*), \sigma_{nn}(x_i^*), \gamma_{nn}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{nn}(y_i^*), \sigma_{nn}(y_i^*), \gamma_{nn}(y_i^*) \rangle$

Step 2: Deliberate the association between the attributes and the alternatives.

Step:3 Deliberate the similarity measure using the formula $S_M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)]$ as proposed in the definition 3.1.

Step:4 Ranking of alternatives.

The alternatives are ranked by the decision makers and it is ranked in inclined form of similarity measure $S_M[(I_1, I_2), (J_1, J_2)]$. The towering value of the similarity measure gives the best alternative.

	(I_{M_1}, I_{F_1})	(I_{M_2}, I_{F_2}) (I_{M_N}, I_{F_n})
(J_{M_1}, J_{F_1})	$\langle \mu_{11}(x_i^*), \sigma_{11}(x_i^*), \gamma_{11}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{11}(y_i^*), \sigma_{11}(y_i^*), \gamma_{11}(y_i^*) \rangle$	$\langle \mu_{12}(x_i^*), \sigma_{12}(x_i^*), \gamma_{12}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{12}(y_i^*), \sigma_{12}(y_i^*), \gamma_{12}(y_i^*) \rangle$ $\langle \mu_{1n}(x_i^*), \sigma_{1n}(x_i^*), \gamma_{1n}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{1n}(y_i^*), \sigma_{1n}(y_i^*), \gamma_{1n}(y_i^*) \rangle$
...
...
...
(J_{M_N}, J_{F_n})	$\langle \mu_{n1}(x_i^*), \sigma_{n1}(x_i^*), \gamma_{n1}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{n1}(y_i^*), \sigma_{n1}(y_i^*), \gamma_{n1}(y_i^*) \rangle$	$\langle \mu_{n2}(x_i^*), \sigma_{n2}(x_i^*), \gamma_{n2}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{n2}(y_i^*), \sigma_{n2}(y_i^*), \gamma_{n2}(y_i^*) \rangle$ $\langle \mu_{nn}(x_i^*), \sigma_{nn}(x_i^*), \gamma_{nn}(x_i^*) \rangle, \langle \mu_{nn}(y_i^*), \sigma_{nn}(y_i^*), \gamma_{nn}(y_i^*) \rangle$

5. Numerical Example

For the employees, it is important to invest a sum of money in a good manner to reduce their annual income tax amount. Also, the investing amount should be safer and profitable. So, the employees struggles to decide which investment is better to choose. The investment should be chosen properly, otherwise the employees will face heavy loss or bad impact to their economic condition. The mathematical decision making method is used to find the proper investment opinion, so that the employees can add some amount of money for their future requirements and to less the money to be paid for income tax.

The proposed method includes neutrosophic binary truth membership, neutrosophic binary indeterminacy and neutrosophic binary false membership values.

Consider a set of employees: Male and Female. They were represented by $M = \{M_1, M_2, M_3, M_4, M_5\}$ and $F = \{F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4, F_5\}$. Here M_1 represents the male employees who are less than 25 years of age, M_2 represent the male employees of 25 – 35 years of age, M_3 represent the male employees of 35 – 45 years of age, M_4 represent the male employees of 45 – 55 years of age and M_5 represent the male employees who are above 55 years. Similarly, F_1 represents the female employees who are less than 25 years of age, F_2 represent the female employees of 25 – 35 years of age, F_3 represent the female employees of 35 – 45 years of age, F_4 represent the female employees of 45 – 55 years of age and F_5 represent the female employees who are above 55 years. Assume that, the employee decides to invest the money to a best investing sectors : Public Provident Fund (I_{M_1}, I_{F_1}) , Stock Market (I_{M_2}, I_{F_2}) , Gold bond (I_{M_3}, I_{F_3}) , Postal Life Insurance (I_{M_4}, I_{F_4}) and Real Estate (I_{M_5}, I_{F_5}) . The investment of money will be decided by the employees according to the following attributes: Growth Analysis (J_{M_1}, J_{F_1}) , Risk Analysis (J_{M_2}, J_{F_2}) , High Annual Return (J_{M_3}, J_{F_3}) , Norms and conditions (J_{M_4}, J_{F_4}) and Market Analysis (J_{M_5}, J_{F_5}) . Our aim is to find the perfect investing sector.

In this application part, the collection of investment data plays a vital role in understanding the decision making factors of individuals on the basis of investment. The Google form was

used to collect these investment data from the employees of various sectors (both public and private). The google form consists of sixteen questions which includes Demographic Details, Income, Experience, Investment Preferences and the various attributes of the investment preferences.

The google form consists of multiple choice questions, open-ended responses and so on. The google form was send to the employees of different sector via email and other communicating media. More than hundred and fifty employees responded it. The collected data consists of the following key variabilities:

- Demographic details: It consists of age, gender, occupation etc.,
- Investement preference : It includes the type of investments, risk factors and investment goals.
- Investment Experience : It covers the previous investment experience and the knowledge level in investment
- Decision-making factors: It consists of the attributes of the investment sectors.

The relation between the employees and the attributes is represented in the form of neutrosophic binary sets in the table 3.

	(J_{M_1}, J_{F_1})	(J_{M_2}, J_{F_2})	(J_{M_3}, J_{F_3})	(J_{M_4}, J_{F_4})	(J_{M_5}, J_{F_5})
(M_1, F_1)	< 0.6, 0.2, 0.4 >, < 0.8, 0.3, 0.2 >	< 0.65, 0.3, 0.35 >, < 0.7, 0.4, 0.3 >	< 0.45, 0.35, 0.53 >, < 0.5, 0.4, 0.5 >	< 0.17, 0.35, 0.82 >, < 0.3, 0.4, 0.7 >	< 0.25, 0.4, 0.75 >, < 0.3, 0.5, 0.7 >
(M_2, F_2)	< 0.68, 0.32, 0.32 >, < 0.7, 0.4, 0.3 >	< 0.75, 0.3, 0.25 >, < 0.65, 0.3, 0.35 >	< 0.3, 0.4, 0.7 >, < 0.45, 0.3, 0.53 >	< 0.29, 0.17, 0.17 >, < 0.3, 0.5, 0.7 >	< 0.3, 0.15, 0.7 >, < 0.4, 0.2, 0.6 >
(M_3, F_3)	< 0.32, 0.36, 0.68 >, < 0.45, 0.2, 0.53 >	< 0.45, 0.25, 0.55 >, < 0.65, 0.3, 0.55 >	< 0.7, 0.15, 0.3 >, < 0.8, 0.2, 0.2 >	< 0.58, 0.29, 0.41 >, < 0.35, 0.2, 0.65 >	< 0.5, 0.15, 0.5 >, < 0.65, 0.3, 0.35 >
(M_4, F_4)	< 0.4, 0.36, 0.6 >, < 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 >	< 0.35, 0.15, 0.65 >, < 0.58, 0.3, 0.41 >	< 0.6, 0.25, 0.9 >, < 0.5, 0.6, 0.5 >	< 0.7, 0.17, 0.29 >, < 0.68, 0.2, 0.32 >	< 0.4, 0.25, 0.6 >, < 0.25, 0.3, 0.75 >
(M_5, F_5)	< 0.36, 0.32, 0.64 >, < 0.4, 0.2, 0.6 >	< 0.75, 0.15, 0.25 >, < 0.9, 0.2, 0.1 >	< 0.65, 0.25, 0.35 >, < 0.5, 0.2, 0.5 >	< 0.88, 0.35, 0.11 >, < 0.9, 0.2, 0.1 >	< 0.75, 0.2, 0.25 >, < 0.7, 0.3, 0.3 >

TABLE 3. Realtion between Employees and Attributes

The relation between the attributes and the alternatives is represented in the form of neutrosophic binary sets in the table 4.

	(I_{M_1}, I_{F_1})	(I_{M_2}, I_{F_2})	(I_{M_3}, I_{F_3})	(I_{M_4}, I_{F_4})	(I_{M_5}, I_{F_5})
(J_{M_1}, J_{F_1})	< 0.8, 0.12, 0.2 >, < 0.6, 0.2, 0.4 >	< 0.8, 0.3, 0.2 >, < 0.7, 0.1, 0.3 >	< 0.7, 0.5, 0.3 >, < 0.4, 0.4, 0.6 >	< 0.2, 0.5, 0.7 >, < 0.4, 0.2, 0.6 >	< 0.75, 0.4, 0.25 >, < 0.4, 0.1, 0.6 >
(J_{M_2}, J_{F_2})	< 0.4, 0.32, 0.6 >, < 0.5, 0.2, 0.5 >	< 0.9, 0.15, 0.1 >, < 0.8, 0.2, 0.2 >	< 0.85, 0.25, 0.15 >, < 0.7, 0.1, 0.3 >	< 0.9, 0.2, 0.05 >, < 0.8, 0.1, 0.2 >	< 0.65, 0.35, 0.35 >, < 0.7, 0.3, 0.3 >
(J_{M_3}, J_{F_3})	< 0.6, 0.32, 0.4 >, < 0.8, 0.2, 0.2 >	< 0.35, 0.15, 0.75 >, < 0.4, 0.2, 0.6 >	< 0.9, 0.3, 0.1 >, < 0.8, 0.5, 0.2 >	< 0.29, 0.23, 0.7 >, < 0.3, 0.1, 0.7 >	< 0.95, 0.15, 0.05 >, < 0.8, 0.3, 0.2 >
(J_{M_4}, J_{F_4})	< 0.52, 0.2, 0.48 >, < 0.4, 0.1, 0.6 >	< 0.75, 0.4, 0.28 >, < 0.8, 0.3, 0.2 >	< 0.65, 0.25, 0.35 >, < 0.7, 0.1, 0.3 >	< 0.9, 0.47, 0.05 >, < 0.6, 0.5, 0.4 >	< 0.9, 0.15, 0.1 >, < 0.8, 0.3, 0.2 >
(J_{M_5}, J_{F_5})	< 0.8, 0.32, 0.2 >, < 0.7, 0.2, 0.3 >	< 0.9, 0.15, 0.1 >, < 0.9, 0.5, 0.1 >	< 0.75, 0.4, 0.25 >, < 0.8, 0.2, 0.2 >	< 0.88, 0.29, 0.12 >, < 0.9, 0.3, 0.1 >	< 0.35, 0.4, 0.65 >, < 0.7, 0.2, 0.3 >

TABLE 4. Relation between the Attributes and Alternatives

The computation of Similarity measure between the employees and the investing sectors is shown in the following table:

	(I_{M_1}, I_{F_1})	(I_{M_2}, I_{F_2})	(I_{M_3}, I_{F_3})	(I_{M_4}, I_{F_4})	(I_{M_5}, I_{F_5})
(M_1, F_1)	0.2907	0.3005	0.2823	0.2428	0.2918
(M_2, F_2)	0.3139	0.3267	0.3957	0.2728	0.2986
(M_3, F_3)	0.3927	0.2888	0.3698	0.3955	0.3281
(M_4, F_4)	0.2844	0.2906	0.3191	0.3468	0.3999
(M_5, F_5)	0.4108	0.3773	0.3908	0.3778	0.3889

The highest similarity measure describes the best investigating sector. Therefore, the employees of less than 25 years of age chooses stock market, the employees of 25 to 35 years of age chooses Gold bond, the employees of 35 to 45 years chooses Postal Life Insurance and 45 to 55 years of age chooses Real Estate, the employees of above 55 years of age chooses Public Provident Fund as the best investing sector.

6. Conclusion

The main goal of this paper is to help a employee invest in a good manner. The basic purpose of this paper lies in ascertaining the good investment method. In addition, the researcher applied the neutrosophic binary sets in finding the highest unemployment rate. From this paper, it is evident that mathematics has been a key element to gather more information and is a best tool for solving the real life decision making problems.

7. Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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